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4. Resilience issues of the electric power systems

Automatic over-frequency control scheme implementation

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The EU Network Code on Requirements for Grid Connection of Generators (2016/631) mandates that generators be equipped with limited frequency sensitive mode — over-frequency (LFSM-O) controllers to decrease active power production when frequency exceeds a designated level and according to the predicted droop. In cases where LFSM-O controllers are insufficient, the EU Network Code on Emergency and Restoration (2017/2196) permits the establishment of an automatic over-frequency control scheme, which involves a step-wise linear disconnection of generation within a load frequency control (LFC) area. During the signing of the Synchronous Area Framework Agreement (SAFA) for Continental Europe in 2019, TSOs from South-East Europe (non-EU countries) required derogations from LFSM-O requirements. Subsequently, the Serbian TSO initiated development activities through EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation projects, Crossbow and R²D², to devise technical solutions for an automatic over-frequency control scheme at both national and regional levels. This initiative aims to replicate the response of a system with fully equipped LFSM-O controllers, additionally ensuring that, during significant frequency increases, power flows between LFC areas remain stable to prevent transmission lines tripping and system collapse. The recognized basic technical solutions include remote assignment of the set point to the generator, remote individual shutdown of generators in series or groups, and remote setting of local over-frequency protection. Furthermore, these studies explored transitional solutions leveraging existing local over-frequency protections with static (annual) settings to enhance system responsiveness. The researchers' ambitions also went the other way, so a proposal was made to amend the SAFA Policy on Emergency and Restoration in the part related to the automatic over-frequency control scheme. This paper details the conceptual solutions arising from these projects and the forthcoming implementation in the Serbian transmission system.

Key words: Emergency, Over-frequency, Automatic over-frequency control scheme

1. INTRODUCTION

Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/631 establishing a network code on grid connection requirements for power-generating modules (RfG) [1] sets out harmonized connection rules for power-generating modules. Among other things, this network code introduced a new mechanism for frequency control at elevated frequency levels, known as LFSM-O (Limited Frequency Sensitive Mode – Overfrequency). Its purpose is to reduce the generation of active power by the generating unit at high frequency, according to the specified characteristics. The characteristics of LFSM-O are shown in Figure 1 (the figure is taken from the RfG network code).

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the LFSM-O characteristic

It is important to note that the network code does not define all parameters, but only specifies their allowable ranges. As a result, preliminary studies were conducted for the synchronous area of Continental Europe, which led to the following key conclusions:

- A setpoint of 5% is recommended, but any value within the range of 2-12% is allowed
- The response threshold for LFSM-O was set at 50.2 Hz
- The response time for LFSM-O (for 50% of the required power change) was estimated to be 1 second for solar panels, 2 seconds for wind turbines, and 8 seconds for large synchronous generators
- The value of RoCoF (rate of change of frequency) was set at 2 Hz/s

However, these requirements apply to new generating units, while older generating units, which dominate the generation mix in the Western Balkan region, do not have this functionality. As a result, the power system as a whole does not respond as desired in the event of elevated frequencies.

On the other hand, Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/2196 establishing a network code on emergency and restoration (NC ER) [2] allows for the existence of an automatic overfrequency protection scheme, which would limit frequency deviation by disconnecting generation units. However, this network code itself does not provide a detailed description of the characteristics of this system, but instead states the following in Article 16.3:

"If the LFSM-O does not exist or is not sufficient to fulfil the requirements set out in points (a) and (b) of paragraph 2, each TSO shall set up in addition a step-wise linear disconnection of generation in its LFC area. The TSO shall establish the maximum size of the steps for disconnection of power generating modules and/or of HVDC systems in consultation with the other TSOs of its synchronous area."

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In 2019, when signing the operational agreement for the synchronous area of Continental Europe (SAFA), TSOs from the Western Balkans region reported derogations to Article 16.3. EMS (the Serbian TSO) initiated actions to address this derogation, and through two EU Horizon projects, Crossbow [3] and R²D² [4], developed certain solutions that are currently being implemented in practice. The main idea was to use NC ER Article 16 to compensate for the lack of the LFSM-O controllers in the system. The following sections of this paper provide an overview of the main conclusions and solutions developed within these projects.

2. CROSSBOW PROJECT DEVELOPMENT

As part of the Crossbow project [3], the basic concepts for how an automatic overfrequency protection system (AOFPS) could operate were developed, both at the national and regional levels. The idea of a unified regional system for all users of the SCC (Regional Security Center in Belgrade) emerged during communication among the TSOs from Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Montenegro, all of whom were participants in this project.

Before addressing specific technical solutions for the high-frequency protection system without LFSM-O, it was necessary to outline the basic requirements that any proposed solution should meet. In this context, the following points were identified:

- The AOFPS should have an effect at the transmission system level similar to that of a system where all generation units are equipped with LFSM-O
- The AOFPS must account for dynamic changes in the production schedule
- It is desirable for the AOFPS response time to be as fast as possible. Previous sections outlined recommendations for LFSM-O response times for different production technologies. As a reference, the under-frequency protection system response time requirement is 300 ms
- The final requirement pertains to potential control actions that could reduce the overall production output in the system. In this case, the network code is clear, stating that the AOFPS should be based on linear disconnection of generator units in steps
- The AOFPS should not include generators that are equipped with LFSM-O

At the outset of the project, algorithms for frequency calculation for generator disconnection were developed. These algorithms were based on real-time measurements, with calculations repeated every few minutes (making it a close-to-real-time system). In this context, two algorithms were developed at the national level. The first, simpler algorithm provided settings for high-frequency protection for each generator in a predefined priority array, which would be defined in collaboration with the TSO and the producer (each generator would have a different disconnection frequency). The disconnection frequency is determined according to the following formula (corresponding to the recommended LFSM-O droop of 5% and 50,2 Hz of activation frequency):

$$f_{disci} \text{ [Hz]} = (2008 + 0,5 \cdot P_{geni} + \sum P_{gen(1 \rightarrow i-1)})/40, \text{ where:}$$

- f_{disci} – disconnection frequency for the generator in the i -th place in the array
- P_{geni} – active power of the generator at the i -th position in the array
- $\sum P_{gen(1 \rightarrow i-1)}$ – the sum of the active powers of the generator at the first to $i-1$ place in the array

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The second, more complex algorithm involved the creation of multiple steps for high-frequency protection, meaning that within each step, several generators would be disconnected at the same frequency. Within the project, 8 disconnection steps were adopted with the following frequencies: 50.20 Hz, 50.40 Hz, 50.60 Hz, 50.80 Hz, 51.00 Hz, 51.25 Hz, 51.50 Hz, and 51.75 Hz. These steps are designed to disconnect a cumulative total of 4%, 12%, 20%, 28%, 37%, 47%, 57%, and 67% of the total production (Figure 2). Since the protection device has up to 6 frequency protection steps, the following approach was adopted: a) hydro generators have steps I-VI of the over-frequency protection, b) wind generators and smaller thermal generators have steps II-VII, and c) large thermal generators have steps III-VIII. The challenge was to achieve sufficient accuracy in this algorithm. A minimum accuracy of 7% was adopted, as it is the required accuracy for under-frequency protection. The adopted algorithm achieved an accuracy of around 1%.

Figure 2. Graphical representation of the AOFPS effects (generation disconnection in steps)

The next step was to develop algorithms at the regional level. The problem that the regional algorithm needed to solve was ensuring that the response of the AOFPS did not disrupt power flows between involved LFC areas, which could potentially cause a new disturbance. The input data for the regional algorithm came from the results of the national algorithm, where the disconnection frequency for each generator was calculated. The regional algorithm aggregates all generators into a sequence based on increasing disconnection frequencies, and for each generator disconnection, it calculates the change in power flows on the interconnecting transmission lines and compares this with the Available Transmission Cross-Border Capacity remaining after market allocations. The effect of the disconnection is simulated through Power Transfer Distribution Factor (PTDF) matrices. If it was determined that the disconnection of a particular generator violated this criterion, the next generator in the sequence, which would satisfy the criterion, would be selected, and a new disconnection frequency would be assigned according to the algorithm used at the national level. Testing showed that in the vast majority of analyzed cases, this criterion could be maintained up to a frequency of 52 Hz, which was considered more than sufficient.

Once the algorithms were resolved, the next step was to address the method of generator disconnection. Two solutions were developed. The first solution was based on sending a disconnection signal from the AOFPS to the generator in the usual manner. This method was demonstrated through the WAMPAC system, produced by the Slovenian company ELPROS, which also participated in the Crossbow project (Figure 3). The second method is more interesting and technically demanding. The idea here is for the AOFPS to send information to the protection device at the generator's connecting line and adjust the disconnection frequency value. This solution is applicable only to the algorithm where generators are disconnected in steps based on over-

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frequency protection, as the protection devices allow the setting of multiple disconnection frequency values. The AOFPS sends a signal that deactivates one value and activates another. This technical solution was also successfully demonstrated. However, it turned out that this solution requires the most advanced systems in terms of local control and protection, and it can only be applied in a very limited number of facilities.

Figure 3. Graphical representation of the AOFPS developed in Crossbow project

At the end of the project, the shortcomings of these solutions were evaluated, and recommendations for further improvements were provided (note – full implementation of the AOFPS requires extensive communication with electricity producers, which was not possible within the scope of the project). The first issue is the remote disconnection of generators, or the risk that the AOFPS could send incorrect disconnection signals. This problem can be addressed within the local protection system, where the effect of the signal would be conditioned by the measured local frequency. The second issue is that the available downward reserve is not utilized; instead, generators are immediately disconnected. The problem lies in the NC ER itself, which does not foresee this option, and additionally, this network code does not sufficiently detail the conditions for the AOFPS. Third, such solutions work well when the system is interconnected, but due to the limitations of the project's resources, a solution for system split was not developed.

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3. R²D² PROJECT DEVELOPMENT

As we mentioned, one of the biggest criticisms of the solution from the Crossbow project [3] is that it does not utilize downward reserve (although it is questionable whether the response time is satisfactory). Therefore, within the R²D² project [4], the focus was on improving the AOFPS (in this project, it was referred to as the Over-Frequency Protection Module (OFPM), which is one component of the broader IRIS product) to incorporate this missing functionality. Below is a description of how this functionality was implemented.

The OFPM is primarily designed for power plants that can quickly respond to a power reduction signal. In the case of the Serbian LFC Area, this includes Hydro Power Plants (HPP), Gas Power Plants (GPP), and Wind Parks (WP). Since WPs have priority for system access, power reduction is carried out according to the following hierarchy: 1) HPP, 2) GPP, 3) WP.

The formula for determining the needed power reduction at the level of LFC Area in case of over-frequency (P_{pr}) is (corresponding to the LFSM-O droop of 5% and 50,2 Hz of activation frequency):

$$P_{pr} [\%] = 40 \cdot f - 2008, \text{ where } f \text{ represents frequency in Hz.}$$

For each synchronous generator or power plant, the amount of active power it can reduce is known, based on SCADA measurements and the technical specifications for aFRR/mFRR control. This reduction is applied in proportion to the available downward aFRR/mFRR reserve for the respective group of generators.

Next, for each generator is calculated:

$$P_{di} = P_i - P_{mini}, \text{ where:}$$

- P_{di} – available downward active power for generator 'i'
- P_i – current active power for generator 'i'
- P_{mini} – minimum active power to which the generator can be reduced

The sum of downward reserve for all generators is also calculated - SUM (P_d), as well as by generator type SUM (P_{HPPd}) - hydro power plants, SUM (P_{GPPd}) - gas fired power plants, and SUM (P_{WPD}) - wind parks.

If the total downward reserve for all generators is less than the minimum downward reserve ($P_{threshold}$), the algorithm will automatically proceed to the secondary, generator disconnection mechanism.

Next, the calculation of the reduction base power (set-point) for each generator in this mechanism is performed as follows:

1) If $P_{pr} < \text{SUM} (P_{HPPd})$ then:

- For each hydro-generator, a new base power is determined according to the formula:

$$P_{bi} = P_i - P_{pr} \cdot P_d / \text{SUM} (P_{HPPd}) \text{ where:}$$

- P_{bi} – new base power for the hydro-generator 'i'

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2) If $\text{SUM}(P_{\text{HPPd}}) < P_{\text{pr}} < \text{SUM}(P_{\text{HPPd}}) + \text{SUM}(P_{\text{GPPd}})$ then:

- For each hydro-generator, a new base power equal to its minimum active power in mFRR control is determined
- For each gas fired generator, a new base power is determined according to the formula:

$$P_{\text{bi}} = P_i - [P_{\text{pr}} - \text{SUM}(P_{\text{HPPd}})] \cdot P_{\text{di}} / \text{SUM}(P_{\text{GPPd}})$$

3) If $\text{SUM}(P_{\text{HPPd}}) + \text{SUM}(P_{\text{GPPd}}) < P_{\text{pr}} < \text{SUM}(P_{\text{HPPd}}) + \text{SUM}(P_{\text{GPPd}}) + \text{SUM}(P_{\text{WPD}})$ then:

- For each hydro-generator and gas fired generator, a new base power equal to its minimum active power in mFRR control is determined
- For each Wind Park, a new base power is determined according to the formula:

$$P_{\text{bi}} = P_i - [P_{\text{pr}} - \text{SUM}(P_{\text{HPPd}}) - \text{SUM}(P_{\text{GPPd}})] \cdot P_d / \text{SUM}(P_{\text{WPD}})$$

As the OFPM is planned to activate above 50.2 Hz, this will coincide with the automatic freeze of the aFRP (automated frequency restoration process). This is based on the assumption that the behaviour of the turbine controllers will not interfere with the operation of the OFPM.

In the R²D² project, generator disconnection is defined as a secondary mechanism, applied only if the downward reserve falls below a configurable threshold or if the frequency exceeds a configurable threshold (simpler algorithm developed in the Crossbow project is applied).

Figure 4. OFPM summary display

The validation of these mechanisms was carried out through simulations in the MATLAB environment, and the following results were obtained (10 tests were performed, and only one of them is presented here with the simulation results).

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This test aimed to show the activation only the first mechanism of the OFPM tool, for such conditions when the total active power to be reduced is less than the sum of the available capacity for active power reduction on all hydro power and thermal power units already connected to electrical system. This means that the algorithm should send set-point values equal to active power production on technical minimum to all hydro power units and set-point values to thermal power units in accordance with the calculation methodology. Additionally, OFPM should send set-point value to wind farms equal to the active power output of each farm at the moment of activation OFPM in order to limit their production due to a potential increase in wind speed, which is also simulated. Calculation results and responses after simulation are shown in figures below. In all figures, the dashed vertical red lines define the time frame of OFPM activation, beginning and ending.

Figure 5 shows simulated system frequency over time.

Figure 5. System frequency

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Figure 6. Available capacity for active power reduction for each type of power plant

In Figure 6, each coloured line shows the sum of the available capacity for reducing active power on all generation units of the same type over the time, e.g. hydro-blue line, thermal-orange line and wind-yellow line. Available capacity for reducing active power is recalculated in each cycle (2 sec) for each generation unit as the difference between the current active power production and operational minimum value.

Figure 7. Calculated active power that needs to be reduced

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Depending on the system frequency and the selected droop, the OFPM calculates the amount of active power that needs to be reduced to decrease the system frequency to a value at least equal to 50.2 Hz, in the Figure 7 marked with P_{dec} . The algorithm performs calculations in each cycle regarding the change in the system frequency and new inputs of current active power production of generation units.

Figure 8. Active power response of HPP Đerdap 1

Trend diagram of the active power response of the HPP Đerdap 1 (representing all HPPs) is shown in Figure 8. For HPPs, each generator receives a set-point equal to its technical minimum.

Figure 9. Active power response of TPP Pančevo

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Figure 9 shows trend diagram of the active power response of the TPP Pančevo. The only TPP in this mechanism receives a signal for a new set-point that is higher than its technical minimum), to achieve the calculated P_{dec} at the LFC Area level.

Figure 10. Active power response of WPP Alibunar

Trend diagram of the active power response of the WPP Alibunar (representing all involved WPPs) is shown in Figure 10. Since the calculated P_{dec} is achieved by reducing the active power at the HPPs and TPPs, the WPPs only receive a set-point that limits the active power to the level at the moment the OFPM is activated, thereby preventing an increase in generation due to higher wind speeds (see Figure 11).

Figure 81. Wind speed change

Figure 12. OFPM simplified control architecture

The OFPM is integrated with the SCADA/EMS system, which facilitates communication with power plants. SCADA collects data on base power, active power of power plants/generators, frequency, and generator status, while also sending setpoints and commands. Since active power correction at certain plants is managed by AGC (Automatic Generation Control) under normal operating conditions (when the frequency falls outside the OFPM operational range), the same SCADA command for OFPM control mode can be used to minimize intervention at the power plants during OFPM testing. Furthermore, some wind and thermal power plants have setpoints that the OFPM can utilize, reducing the need for intervention. An alternative approach would be to implement new setpoints specifically for the OFPM, which would require intervention at the plants. The system described includes two SCADA/EMS systems, with only one responsible for sending commands and setpoints. For AGC, the system from which commands are sent can be switched by configuring both systems to determine which one will operate. All of these communications are illustrated in Figure 12 where OFPM simplified control architecture is presented.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the activities involved in developing a centralized system to replace the non-existent LFSM-O controllers on generator units. To develop the replacement system, Serbian TSO utilized two EU Horizon projects. In the first, the Crossbow project, conceptual solutions were explored, while the second, R²D², served as the implementation project. At the time of writing this paper, the OFPM is being integrated with the SCADA system at the national control center of Serbian TSO. In this way, this TSO will be able to ensure an appropriate system-wide response to high frequencies by reducing generation and/or disconnecting generators from the grid.

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However, the development of this tool does not end here, as it still lacks the necessary functionalities in the event of a system split. To address these shortcomings, it is essential to integrate this tool with another one developed in the EU Horizon projects Trinity and R²D², namely the Emergency & Restoration (E&R) tool, which includes a system split module. This tool, based on topology and frequency measurements, can identify islanded sub-systems and determine which generator is located in which island. A methodology has also been developed to calculate the missing or excess power in each island. By linking the OFPM with the E&R system split module, the OFPM will be able to generate signals for each island individually, thus eliminating the final limitation of the centralized AOFPS.

Finally, it should be noted that the work on the mentioned EU Horizon projects has contributed to the improvement of emergency and restoration rules for the synchronous area of Continental Europe. At the time of writing this paper, work is ongoing to amend these rules, which foresee the activation of LFSM-O controllers at 50.2 Hz with a droop of 5%. Additionally, recommendations are provided for an automatic over-frequency control scheme, which aligns with the solutions described in this paper.

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